

CLIMATE CHANGE AND HUMAN SECURITY: CRITICAL STUDY

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Abstract

Pakistan is among the five most climate affected countries, facing severe natural disasters, agricultural disruption, and water scarcity. Climate change threatens human security, amplifying social and economic instability, particularly for vulnerable populations. To address these challenges, Pakistan is advancing resilience through disaster risk reduction, sustainable agriculture, renewable energy, and water resource management. Cooperative research, capacity building, and technological transfers form the backbone of these initiatives, promoting clean energy adoption and agricultural sustainability. Supported by the US Alliance, these efforts emphasize innovation, job creation, and public health improvements. Inclusive governance and participatory decision making are central to ensuring equitable adaptation strategies, especially for marginalized communities. Effective resilience measures are essential for Pakistan's sustainable development in the face of escalating climate risks.

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INTRODUCTION

Climate change signifies a long-term alteration in temperature and weather patterns, driven by both natural factors and human activities, notably the combustion of fossil fuels that results in greenhouse gas emissions contributing to global warming. Since the 19th century, significant weather changes underscore that human actions have primarily propelled climate change. Pakistan stands out, ranking as the fifth most affected nation by extreme weather events driven by climate change, with glacial lake outburst floods (GLOF) and flash floods severely impacting various regions. The consequences are dire, claiming over 1,500 lives and displacing millions who now reside in relief camps. Environmental degradation hampers Pakistan's economic well-being, with the World Bank reporting a 2016 cost of US \$25.1 billion due to air, water, and soil pollution, equating to 8.96% of GDP. Factors such as unregulated deforestation, rapid population

growth, unorganized industrial expansion, and inadequate resource management exacerbate this issue, contributing to climate change in the country. Vulnerable populations reliant on natural resources experience heightened risks due to these environmental challenges. The stark reality for Pakistan, hosting 7,000 glaciers and 36 glacial lakes, is underscored by severe flooding that has led to over 1,730 fatalities and widespread displacement. With less than 1% contribution to global greenhouse gas emissions, Pakistan bears the brunt of the impacts caused by industrialized nations. Economic repercussions from recent floods reach an estimated US \$15.2 billion, exacerbating human security crises as millions lack shelter and resources for the winter. The floods have severely affected agricultural land, damaged infrastructure including 3,161 kilometers of roads and 149 bridges, leading to health and food crises. Furthermore, incidents of

personal security threats, such as the abduction and assault of a minor girl in Karachi, illustrate the emerging human security threats arising from climate change's aftermath, including flash floods and glacial lake outbursts.

Methodology

This study adopts a **mixed method approach**, combining both quantitative and qualitative content analysis. The purpose is to evaluate the effect of climate change on human life, with a specific focus on Pakistan as the case study. By integrating numerical data with thematic insights, the research aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of climate change impacts.

Climate Change

According to the International Panel on Climate Change IPCC's 5th Assessment Report, anthropogenic activities were to blame for the climatic change that occurred. Climate change is defined as "a change in the climate that is attributable to human activity, either directly or indirectly, and that over comparable time periods modifies both the natural variability of the climate and the composition of the global atmosphere. "Various factors cause the global climate to change continuously. The slow, centuries-long transformation did not raise many red flags, and other environmental issues were still being discussed. The scientific world, however, was driven to thoroughly investigate the causes by the current trend, which started about five decades ago. Dressler and Parson highlight human-caused factors, but they also mention other factors such geological processes, orbital variation, solar variability, volcanic activity, and earth's internal variability.

Non-Traditional Security

Several academics have reinterpreted the idea of security in the wake of the end of the cold war due to the rising implications of globalization and interconnectedness. Non-traditional security challenges have grown in importance or prominence in the late 20th century. "The Club of Rome group began to produce a series of volumes on the world *problematique* in the 1970s, which were predicated on the idea that there is a complex of problems troubling men of all nations: poverty, degradation of the

environment, alienation of youth, rejection of traditional values, and inflation and other monetary and economic disruption."

NTS-Asia has defined non-traditional security as under: "Non-traditional security issues are the challenges to the survival and well-being of people and states that arise primarily out of non-military sources such as climate change, resource scarcity, infectious disease, natural disasters, irregular migration, food shortage, people smuggling, drug trafficking and transnational crime. These dangers are transnational in scope, defying unilateral remedies and requiring comprehensive – political, economic, social – responses, as well as humanitarian use of military forces."

According to a 1995 report by the Commission on Global Governance, the definition of "global security" must be expanded from the traditional definition of "state security" to also encompass "security of the people and security of the earth," or "environmental security."

The research paper's upcoming chapters will analyze various facets of climate change in order to investigate it as a non-traditional danger to Pakistan's security. Analysis has been done to clearly show how Pakistani securitizing entities view climate change as a threat to the existence of the state.

Security - Copenhagen School

Security has commonly been discussed in relation to realism. Security is defined pretty narrowly in realism, which uses the state as its referent. The use of force, the threat of using force, and the maintenance of a balance of power are common security procedures. Realists view environmental issues as "low politics." The theory of securitization developed by the Copenhagen School, a body of study primarily linked to the work of Barry Buzan and Ole Weaver, is the most creative and thoughtful attempt to conceptualize the social construction of security challenges.

There are no hidden, objective threats, according to the securitization theory. Instead, if a political community successfully uses a speech act to reframe a problem as a security concern, they can be changed from other issues into cyber security threats. In this view, security is not a value or a condition but rather a social practice. That is to say, the approach to

handling a problem will change if it is successful in receiving the categorization of a security problem.

At the Conflict and Peace Research Institute (COPRI).Copenhagen school was born Barry Buzan, Ole Waever, and Jaap de Wilde are the founding professors of this school, which was founded in Copenhagen. The Copenhagen School framework supported widening the definition of security by advocating that the security agenda be evaluated in light of various security concerns. It questioned the conventional notion of security, which maintains that conflict and the creation or use of military power constitute the core of security studies. Additionally, if the other problems endanger the core idea, they can be classified as security challenges. Security, in the words of Buzan et al., "is about survival." They went on to explain the situation by saying that "it occurs when an issue is posed as an existential threat to a selected referent object."

The five broad areas established by the Copenhagen School paradigm;

1. Military,
2. economic,
3. environmental,
4. sociological,
5. political

In order to break away from a traditionalist vision of security, the Copenhagen school concentrated on a multi-sectorial approach. Four out of the five security sectors are non-military. The Copenhagen School broadens and develops the idea of security by including risks from non-state actors. Through the exposure of dangers to the referent objects, the framework develops a more fundamental approach of security studies. Additionally, it describes how these dangers were secured.

CAUSES OF CLIMATE CHANGE IN PAKISTAN

Carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases that are released into the atmosphere by burning fossil fuels are the causes of climate change. The economy, the means of subsistence for the poor and sustainable development are all suffering in Pakistan as a result of environmental degradation and climate change. On the one hand, the environment that led to climate change is under tremendous strain from the expanding population, unplanned urbanization, and reliance on natural resources. Mismanagement of

water and solid waste as well as a lack of public knowledge of environmental issues has made the situation worse. As a result, Pakistan continues to experience numerous natural catastrophes such as floods, earthquakes, landslides, cyclones, and drought that endanger the lives and livelihood of its population. The major factors effecting climate and environmental degradation in Pakistan are highlighted below and these indicators are discussed briefly also:

- I. Global warming
 - a. Green houses gases and its effects
 - b. Generating power (fossil fuel burning)
- II. CPEC developments
- III. Unregulated deforestation & unorganized urbanization
- IV. Burgeoning population

Global Warming and Pakistan

The term "global warming" describes the impact that human activities have on the climate, particularly the burning of fossil fuels (coal, oil, and gas) and extensive deforestation, which release significant amounts of "greenhouse gases" into the atmosphere, the most significant of which is carbon dioxide. These gases operate as blankets over the Earth's surface, absorbing infrared radiation that is emitted by the surface and keeping it warmer than it otherwise would be. Climate changes are linked to this warming. The 'greenhouse effect,' which causes global warming, is widely understood from a scientific perspective.

roads and motorways already constructed either by extension or expansion. Following is a list of Motorways that have to be managed by the National Highway authority:

Routes	From	To	Length
M-1	Islamabad	Peshawar	154 kms
M-2	Lahore	Islamabad	367 kms
M-3	Pindi Bhattian	Multan	53 kms
M-4	Faisalabad	Multan	243 kms
M-5	Multan	DG Khan	84 kms
M-6	DG Khan	Kakkar	467 kms
M-7	Kakkar	Karachi	280kms
M-8	Gawadar	Ratodero	859 kms
M-9	Karachi	Hyderabad	136 kms

Unregulated Deforestation

"Lands of more than 0.5 hectares, with a tree canopy cover of more than 10%, which are not predominantly under agricultural or urban land use," are considered forests. Both the existence of trees and the absence of other major land uses determine the occurrence of forests. The trees must be able to grow to a minimum height of 5 meters where they are planted. Deforestation is an issue worldwide because peasants and the timber mafia frequently take down trees and plants without regard for the future of the environment. Technically speaking, the act of deforestation is described as the removal of huge standing trees, which leads to the subsequent conversion of the affected area to a non-forest usage. For instance, the area that deforestation has cleared could be used for livestock, farming, or urban development. It is significant to note that tropical rainforest regions have experienced the majority of deforestation cases.

The issue has been exacerbated by the low literacy rate, poverty, underdevelopment, and lack of adequate communications and transportation systems for the general populace. Additionally, compared to its real production; demand for wood is substantially higher. The actual cause of deforestation in Pakistan is that there is a significant disparity between the amount of wood that is produced and consumed. A significant timber mafia of wealthy individuals is

engaged in the illicit harvesting and selling of wood despite official restrictions declaring it to be illegal.

Urbanization Encroachment of Agricultural Land
In 1960, 1970, and 1980, with particular attention paid to Pakistan, the country's annual GDP was 6.8%, 4.8%, and 6.5%, respectively. In contrast, this rate decreased by up to 2% in 2000. Agriculture is the main sector in Pakistan's economy. With a GDP share of 24%, it employs more than half of the nation's work force and generates a significant chunk of foreign money by exporting 80% of its agricultural output. However, the rural population is moving to urban areas while using agricultural land, which will make things harder for our nation in the future. In the last 13 years, rapid urbanization turned 3307 acres of agricultural land into built-up areas; the reduction was brought on by the lack of rules to prevent this conversion. Both the ecology and the food supply are negatively impacted by this change. Situation is continuously worsening as concrete structures have been built on farmland, especially along the sides of the Grand Trunk Road, touching nearby close areas. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP) has a shortage in wheat output in particular. According to the Bureau of Statistics Planning and Development's development statistics for KP-2016, the region's total production of wheat in 2015-16 was 1155 tones, compared to a predicted 3056 tones, representing a deficit of 1901 tones.

The primary cause of the decreasing agricultural land is the massive migration from the various regions of KP and the influx of Afghan refugees. For cities to be sustainable, master plans are essential. Because Peshawar's 1965 first master plan was never carried out, the city's chaotic urbanization is the result. In order to supervise urban growth, the Peshawar Developmental Authority was founded in 1987.

Unfortunately, the four municipal towns of Peshawar did not see any success with the concrete construction regulating authorities' initial efforts. Housing projects being set up by the provincial and federal governments require a sizable amount of land. A 10,000 kanal stretch along Nasir Bagh Road marks the beginning of phase I of the military-owned Defense Housing Authority's development plan. Phase II of the same project will involve the purchase of more than 5000 acres in the communities of Budni, Wodpaga, and Yaseen Abad. The Civil Aviation Authority is also preparing to acquire roughly 2000 acres in the Mattani neighbourhood for the suggested airport.

IMPACTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON PAKISTAN

The global climate crisis poses a number of threats well-being and prosperity of people of Pakistan. Pakistan is predominantly an agrarian state and agriculture is a vital source of employment for 42 percent of its population. Almost all of agricultural land depends on irrigation from River Indus and its canals which basically come from glacial melt. Climate change has fastened the glacier melt, which will increase the incidence of GLOF (glacial lake outburst floods) and flash-floods downstream and this will increasingly affect agriculture-related activities, food production and livelihoods. Already, 39 percent of the population of Pakistan experiences multidimensional poverty. Furthermore, it would impact health of internally displaced persons (IDPs) through heat exhaustion, malnutrition and the increased burden of waterborne diseases and contagious diseases.

Pakistan is a country which is host of 7000 glaciers & 36 glacial lakes in Gilgit Baltistan (GB). Climate change has hit Pakistan severely and ranked 5th worst

countries affected by extreme weather conditions caused by climate change. Recent floods have claimed more than 1730 lives with millions displaced (IDPs) sheltered themselves in relief camps.

Furthermore, Pakistan is reaping whatever being sowed by industrialized countries whereas its contribution to global greenhouse gases is less than 1%. Economic losses due to the devastation by floods reached to 15.2 billion US dollars (WORLD BANK). Millions of people are going into winter without shelter and livelihood, which the premier of Pakistan Shehbaz Sharif mentioned in COP 27, which is leading to human security crises. Agricultural lands affected by floods and stagnant water and infrastructure damages include 3161 kilo-meters of roads and 149 bridges in Pakistan led to health and food crises in peripheries.

In addition, flood-affected minor girl was abducted and gang-raped in Karachi which raises question to Personal Security. (DAILY TIMES)

Glacial Lake Out-Burst Floods (GLOF)

Gilgit-Baltistan has 36 glacial lakes that have been deemed unsafe, and seven of them pose the greatest threat to the population. The chief of the Pakistan Meteorological Department (PMD) was in G-B on an official trip, where flash floods brought on by monsoon rains and melting glaciers had destroyed most of the infrastructure and cost billions of rupees in damages.

GLOFs are listed as a potential threat to communities living in mountainous locations in Pakistan's National Climate Change Policy. The main focus of the relevant policy interventions that have been drafted is on mitigation and adaptation strategies. It proposes keeping an eye on the development of glacial lakes and planning efficient evacuation plans for vulnerable populations in case of a potential flood. With this background, this study aims to examine how distant people in Gilgit-Baltistan perceive risk in order to gain understanding of their risk perception, which can be translated to their readiness, coping mechanisms, and resilience in the event of GLOF incidents. Shrinking of glaciers is vivid in following given image.

Figure: Shrinking of siachen glaciers Source: PMD

Pakistan is home to 7259 glaciers, which cover 11780 square kilometres and have a volume of 2066 cubic kilometres. This region is referred to as the "third pole" of the planet since it contains the most mass. Temperature has a significant impact on the way glaciers grow and melt. Increasing the amount of GHG in the atmosphere can alter long wave radiation, which accelerates the melting of snow and glaciers, according to studies. Because Pakistan is located in the

Indus Basin, the melting of glacial ice, snow, and rain in the catchment areas is the main source of the Indus River System. There will likely be significant melting and draining out of the Himalayan-Karakorum glaciers within the next thirty years, according to studies by numerous think tanks. The region will be most adversely affected by Pakistan's status as a "single basin" nation. Water scarcity would therefore be the result of climate change's greatest impact on Pakistan.

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Source: PMD

The Glacial Lake Outburst Flood (GLOF) phenomena has the potential to unleash devastating torrential floods in the valleys and downstream regions. It poses an increasing threat in areas where glacier melting is accelerating. According to estimations from the Pakistan Meteorological Department, Pakistan has 36 glacial lakes. For individuals who dwell in the at-risk zones, these present a GLOF hazard that is a looming threat. Small-scale initiatives to manage the draining of vulnerable lakes have been carried out in nations like Nepal and Peru in an effort to lessen the chance of a GLOF. These projects can be costly, but Pakistan can also learn from their experiences. Campaign funds is typically available for them, though. But because these communities are more vulnerable than most others to the particular threats that emerge as a result of shifting weather patterns, they require special consideration when it comes to creating adaptable measures to assist them face the difficulties that lie ahead.

Climate Change as A Security Challenge For Pakistan Pakistan currently struggles with a range of issues, including overpopulation, political uncertainties, terrorism, poor government institutions rife with corruption, national discord, a divided economy, weak social structures fueling unrelenting social tensions, and unemployment. The impact of climate change creates a vicious cycle in which already serious socioeconomic issues are made even more difficult.

In the modern era, developing countries which already rely on indigenous renewable resources like agriculture, forests, and fresh water supplies are home to over 90% of population growth.

Pakistan's population is expanding at a pace of 2.4 percent, which is among the fastest growth rates. The resources are put under more stress as a result. Greater hazards related to climate change would be associated with meeting the development needs of a growing population. In addition, the pace of development is slowed by climate change. The long-term effects of climate change include a decrease in rainfall, an increase in the frequency of droughts and floods, and seasonal unpredictability, including greater temperatures and a delayed onset of the colder season. Cycles of crop sowing, maturing, and harvesting are negatively impacted by these shifts. Rising temperatures may particularly lower crop production and promote insect and pest invasions.

Impacts on Agriculture and Human Security

Weather patterns and the severity of weather events are impacted by climate change. For instance, Pakistan's rural economy is vulnerable to the continued availability of water. Not only is water crucial when it is available, but it is also helpful when it is available in the right quantity or within acceptable bounds. It is damaging rather than helpful when there is an excessive amount for a brief period of time as a result of torrential rains. Destructive consequences on the nation's agriculture-based economy can also result from protracted droughts.

People from all over Pakistan, especially those from Sindh province who have lost their livelihood due to water scarcity, travel to Karachi in search of employment. They are forced to live in low-lying slums that are susceptible to cyclones, sea storm surges, and steadily rising sea levels. Every heat wave or downpour shows how unprepared the city's infrastructure is to handle even current emergencies. Intense heat waves, rising sea levels, and storms are just a few of the new threats brought on by climate change that will make Pakistan's security a major problem. The people who live in coastal areas, notably in Karachi, suffer a significant threat to their personal safety due to the Arabian Sea's rising surface temperatures, which also increase the frequency and intensity of sea storms.

Since Pakistan's conventional cropping practices have historically found sufficient water resources to flourish and prosper, any decrease in water availability would be harmful for the agricultural sector. Experts from PIDE conducted a simulation-based study from 2008 to 2030 to visualize the influence of temperature on crops, and they came to the conclusion that the effect of an increase in temperatures varied from crop to crop. For the wheat crop, a 1°C increase in temperature would result in a cumulative loss up to 2030 of 0.02%, while a 2°C increase would result in a collective loss up to 2030 of 0.75% of that in 2008.

Impacts on Human Life

Over 1730 people died as a result of the floods, which affected 33 million people. The poorest and most vulnerable areas are being affected the hardest. More than 8 million displaced individuals are now suffering a health crisis as a result of the scenario, which is still developing with flood waters stagnating in many

locations, causing the development of water-borne and vector-borne diseases.

Following Pakistan's historic floods, a damage, loss, and needs assessment urges "building back better," guided by the ideas of putting the needs of the underprivileged first, transparency, inclusiveness, and environmental protection. According to the study, total economic losses would likely total around USD 15.2 billion, and total damages will likely exceed USD 14.9 billion.

Without including urgently needed additional investments outside of the impacted assets, it is estimated that Pakistan will require at least USD 16.3 billion in rehabilitation and rebuilding to ensure the country's overall ability to withstand future climate shocks and its adaption to climate change. The most substantial losses were in the housing, agriculture and livestock, and transportation and communications sectors, at USD 5.6 billion, USD 3.7 billion, and USD 3.3 billion, respectively. With about 70% of all damages and losses, Sindh is the worst-affected province, followed by Balochistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, and Punjab.

According to the PDNA Human Impact Assessment, the number of individuals living in poverty could rise

by 3.7 to 4.0 percentage points, adding up to 8.4 to 9.1 million more people. It is possible for multidimensional poverty to rise by 5.9 percentage points, putting an additional 1.9 million households at risk of falling into non-financial poverty.

Rehabilitation: A Hope

Massive areas of farms and villages in Pakistan are still under water months after massive floods devastated the country, and over 10 million girls and boys still require immediate, life-saving assistance. According to UNICEF reports, Millions of people continue to live near flooded areas or are vulnerable to flooding.

Numerous families continue to reside in improvised tents next to the road or next to the ruins of their homes, frequently in the open and right next to toxic and stagnant water. Children who are weak and hungry are fighting a lost struggle against acute respiratory infections, severe acute malnutrition, diarrhea, malaria, dengue fever, typhoid, and painful skin disorders. Along with physical diseases, the risk to children's emotional health increases while the crisis drags on.

Figure: A flood effected women standing in the stagnant water

Source : UNICEF

Meanwhile, numerous public health facilities, water systems, and educational institutions have all undergone damage or destruction, along with hundreds of thousands of dwellings. In addition to

continuing to address immediate humanitarian needs, UNICEF will also renovate and repair current educational, water, sanitation, and health facilities for relocating families. However, much more assistance is

required to make sure we can assist all families affected by floods and help them recover from this climatic catastrophe.

Families won't fully recover for months or maybe years due to the extent of the destruction. Some regions have seen an emergency degree of food insecurity, which could have catastrophic long-term effects on the life and wellbeing of children who were already malnourished. Approximately 9 million people are being forced into financial distress and experiencing losses from the floods, while nearly 15 million people in flood-affected areas require urgent food assistance.

FUTURE PROSPECTS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

At Global level, flooding is a significant natural danger. Floods cause destruction of property, fatalities, and subpar economic growth. Although it is impossible to stop floods from happening, their negative consequences can be greatly reduced with careful planning and good preparation. By making precise and timely predictions (forecasting and warning), as well as taking impact-reducing measures, one might lessen their vulnerability to floods. In recent years, flooding has been an issue in Pakistan practically every year. There have been 23 significant flood occurrences in Pakistan between 1947 and 2015, which are estimated to have caused a financial damage of US \$ 38.165 billion. Owing to all these floods, about 12,000 people were killed, and 616,598 km² of land were devastated. Due to high levels of glacial melting, mountain top deicing, and heavy monsoon rainfall, it has been predicted that climate change may increase the frequency and intensity of floods in Pakistan. To minimize flood damages, the scenario calls for effective and long-term flood control.

Construction of Dams

The greatest approach to prevent flooding is to build dams. Dams can control water flow by storing water in reservoirs and lowering the possibility of flooding downstream. The two biggest and most significant flood prevention constructions in Pakistan are the Tarbela Dam and the Mangla Dam. These dams are not entirely efficient, though, as the amount of rainwater they can store before it overflows into rivers below limits the size of their reservoirs. To solve this

issue, the government must construct new dams with bigger reservoirs.

Increase in Plantation, Reforestation & Agricultural Revamp

In Pakistan, increasing the amount of trees and plants in a region is another successful flood prevention strategy. It facilitates the absorption of surplus water and reduces runoff. In Pakistan, the government should plant more trees and plants in places that are prone to floods in order to reduce flooding. Particularly effective at lowering the risk of flooding is *mangroves* and *eucalyptus* trees. They are often known to as "nature's starving tree" due to their extensive root systems. By being placed adjacent to rivers, reservoirs, and bridges, these trees can help reduce tidal wave power, reducing floods and storm surges.

To develop and apply climate-resilient equipment and technologies that can better withstand the effects of flooding and droughts, the agriculture industry also requires increased investment. For instance, more diverse methods of water management for farming, such as rainwater harvesting and regulated aquifer recharge, can help protect agricultural productivity and livelihoods. New types of livestock and crops designed to be more tolerant to climate extremes can also help.

Timely Cleaning of Storm Drains

Storm drains should be properly cleaned as it is one of the most crucial things we can do to avoid floods. During the monsoon, it is extremely crucial. In order to remove extra water from surfaces like pavement and parking lots, storm drains are essential. Nevertheless, they are susceptible to clogging from dirt, leaves, and other debris, which can cause water to back up and finally cause floods. Storm drains should therefore be periodically cleaned, especially before severe rains.

Budget Reallocation

By clearly defining roles and sketching out risk financing instruments, systematize the understanding of catastrophe risk finance in Pakistan. The main stakeholders will gain a better grasp of the pertinent difficulties and how to address them by collaboratively mapping key institutions and existing financing arrangements (and their financial and technical capacity). The visualization could expand on the data

gathered by parties like the ADB, WB, NDMA and NDRMF. Make sure the NDMA and MoF are in charge and are engaging with stakeholders.

The national Disaster Risk Financing Strategy is multispectral, which means that it will require the participation of numerous stakeholders from across the government. As well as development partners, this also includes governmental and non-governmental organizations. For the efforts to be well-coordinated, the process needs to be led by a capable individual. Because of their ability to bring people together, their role in allocating post-disaster funds, and their regular inspection of financial practices throughout the government, ministries of finance are frequently in charge of designing and implementing such projects in other nations. As a local organization addressing the needs of disaster response and recovery, NDMA also plays a significant role in Pakistan. NDMA is also in charge of the National Disaster Management Facility, which might serve as the foundation of the government's security layering strategy.

REFERENCES

- A, Matthew, Richard, Jon Barnett, and Bryan McDonald. *Global Environmental Change and Human Security*. MIT Press, 2009.
- Adaptability and Partnership: Issues for the Strategic Defence Review. London: Stationery Office, 2010.
- Adeel, Zafar, and Robert G. Wirsing. *Imagining Indus: Overcoming Water Insecurity in the Indus Basin*. Springer, 2016.
- AFP. 'Climate Change May Negate Health Gains: Panel'. DAWN.COM, 24 June 2015. <http://www.dawn.com/news/1190040>.
- Ahmad, Dr Shahid. 'Groundwater Management in Pakistan', n.d., 21.
- Ahmadani, Ahmad. 'Pakistan's Population Soars to 207m with 2.4% Growth'. *Pakistan Today*, 25 August 2017. <https://www.pakistantoday.com.pk/2017/08/25/pakistans-population-soars-to-207m-with-2-4-growth/>.
- Ahmed, Beenish. 'Extreme Heat, Fueled By Climate Change, Leaves More Than 800 Dead In Pakistan - ThinkProgress', 24 June 2015. <https://thinkprogress.org/extreme-heat-fueled-by-climate-change-leaves-more-than-800-dead-in-pakistan-554365f9b0b2/>.
- Ahmed, Nafeez. 'Global Water Crisis Causing Failed Harvests, Hunger, War and Terrorism'. *The Ecologist*, 27 March 2015. http://www.theecologist.org/News/news_analysis/2803979/global_water_crisis_causing_failed_harvests_hunger_war_and_terrorism.html.
- Ali, Sajjad, Ying Liu, Muhammad Ishaq, Tariq Shah, Abdullah, Aasir Ilyas, and Izhar Din. 'Climate Change and Its Impact on the Yield of Major Food Crops: Evidence from Pakistan'. *Foods* 6, no. 6 (24 May 2017): 39. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods6060039>.
- Alliance magazine. Interview - Major General Muniruzzaman, March 2012. <http://www.alliancemagazine.org/feature/interview-major-general-muniruzzaman/>.
- Allwood, Julian M., Valentina Bosetti, Navroz K. Dubash, and Luis Gómez-Echeverri, eds. 'Glossary - Climate Change 2014: Contribution of Working Group III to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change'. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2014.
- Altaf, Zafar, Michael Kugelman, Robert M. Hathaway, and Woodrow Wilson International Center for Scholars, eds. *Hunger Pains: Pakistan's Food Insecurity*. Washington, D.C: Woodrow Wilson International Center for Scholars, 2010.
- American Security Project. 'The Global Security Defense Index on Climate Change: Preliminary Results'. American Security Project, 21 March 2013. <https://www.americansecurityproject.org/the-global-security-defense-index-on-climate-change-%ef%bf%bcpreliminary-results/>.
- APP. 'Climate Change to Aggravate Disease Burden, Warns Minister'. DAWN.COM, 11 May 2015. <http://www.dawn.com/news/1181268>.

'As India Reassesses Indus Water Treaty, China Blocks Tributary Of Brahmaputra'.
indiatimes.com. Accessed 4 November 2017.
<http://www.indiatimes.com/news/india/ami-d-rumors-of-india-scrapping-of-indus-water-treaty-with-pakistan-china-blocks-tributary-of-brahmaputra-in-tibet-262741.html>.

